

Pleasure before Duty: Playing and Studying in the Cultic Context of Kharayeb

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Introduction: the Kharayeb Project and the terracotta figurines

The terracotta figurines discovered by Maurice Chéhab and Ibrahim Kaoukabani between 1946 and 1970 in the sanctuary of Kharayeb, a cult place in the hinterland of Tyre (fig. 1), actively contribute to the relation of children's games with education. Since 2009, the study of the assemblage, consisting of about 16.400 fragments, now housed in the storerooms of the National Museum of Beirut, has been part of the *Kharayeb Archaeological Project* directed by Ida Oggiano (Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale – CNR).¹ This larger and ongoing Project includes the excavation of the sanctuary,² the design of an archeological museum on site (KAM),³ the macro- and microscopic examination of fabrics, the petrographic analysis⁴ and the PIXE analytical technique on terracottas and pottery's fabrics.⁵

The terracotta figurines have been analyzed in order to process qualitative and quantitative data, both very important as Arthur Muller recently pointed out.⁶ They were entered in a database and examined in terms of iconographic and stylistic features, as well as technical aspects. Regarding the manufacturing techniques, in the Iron Age and Persian period hand-

1 Cf. Oggiano, 2012a; 2012b; 2012c; 2014; 2015a; 2015b; 2015c; 2018; 2020. I am very thankful to Ida Oggiano for the opportunity to collaborate in the *Kharayeb Archaeological Project* and for her valuable suggestions and comments. A first version of this paper, that is part of an ongoing research, has been presented and profitably discussed at the University of Fribourg, at the workshop ERC Locus Ludi « *Play, Rite and Religion* » (13.3.2019). I warmly thank Véronique Dasen for the helpful remarks as well as the anonymous experts. The images published by Chéhab, 1953-1954, which are re-used here, are still useful reference points to visualize the complete types, since sometimes the figurines are not so clearly understandable, because of their fragmentary state of preservation.

2 Oggiano *et al.*, 2016.

3 <https://shiogumo.com/kam.html>

4 Petrographic analyses are carried out by Giovanni Boschian (University of Pisa).

5 Roumie *et al.*, 2019.

6 Muller, 2017-2018.

made and single moulds productions were widespread,⁷ while in the Hellenistic period double moulds were mostly used, determining a massive production. It is also possible to appreciate the traces of still visible colors applied over the white slip to render details. The fabrics' types are characterized by the presence of many microfossils and numerous small rounded rock inclusions, which suggests that the production was carried out in workshops near the coast – probably in Tyre.⁸

1. The archaeological context

The sanctuary of Kharayeb, located in the hilly country of southern Lebanon, was certainly linked to its hinterland, dependent on the countryside and also connected to some coastal centers, such as the nearby Tyre.

The previous excavations of the site (1946-1970) did not adopt a precise stratigraphic method and did not yield a cogent chronology. They aimed at discovering structures and collecting the archaeological material,⁹ while the new excavations provided a more precise chronological framework for the complex in use from the 7th to the 1st century BCE, and they allowed a reconstruction of the context.¹⁰ After an intense frequentation during the Paleolithic, the first occupation dates back to the Iron Age II/Persian Period (with pottery dating back to the 9th-8th cent. BCE), when the area was chosen for cult practices.¹¹ Probably in the early Hellenistic period, the previous buildings were obliterated by a square edifice, with a large paved courtyard and a rectangular room; finally, a *favissa* was made (fig. 2). The walls were built using blocks extracted from the quarries located upstream of the cult place, and they were covered with plaster, both outside and inside, and with a probable interior stucco decoration. The external part had an Egyptian gorge type cornice and a lintel with traces of red colour, decorated with a sun disk flanked by *uraei*.¹² These architectonic elements were typical of sacred buildings located in the area of Tyre and make evident the connection between the Kharayeb cult place and its coastal hinterland.

2. The two groups of figurines: stratigraphic and chronological frameworks

The figurine assemblage from the old excavations can be chronologically divided into two main groups.¹³

The first one (c. 7th/6th-first half of the 4th cent. BCE) consists of a few local-type figurines, generally hand-made or created using single moulds. They are mostly inspired by the regional

7 The terracotta figurines dating to these two periods are completely modeled by hands or by means of a single mould used to shape the front, while the back is unmodeled or just refined with some simple tools.

8 Cf. Roumie *et al.*, 2019.

9 Chéhab, 1951-1952 and 1953-1954; Kaoukabani, 1973.

10 Oggiano *et al.*, 2016; Oggiano, 2018.

11 Oggiano *et al.*, 2016, p. 198-203 (Nuñez Calvo) and p. 206-210 (Oggiano); Oggiano, 2018, p. 18; 2020, p. 268.

12 Oggiano, 2018.

13 Cf. Oggiano, 2015a and 2015b.

iconographic repertoire, also well documented in Palestine and Cyprus (women holding their breasts, pregnant women, horsemen, horses and chariots, drum players, aso). Already in this period the Eastern-Greek style inspired some types, like the *korai* with a cross-shaped body, a peculiar Eastern feature, wearing *chiton* and *polos* recalling Greek fashion. Some figurines represent Egyptian deities, like Bes, and an Egyptianising local god, seated and wearing an Osiris crown.

The overwhelming majority of the terracottas belongs to the second group which dates to the Hellenistic period, with a broader variety of iconographies, inspired by Egyptian, Greek and local patterns. Few deities are attested (4,6% of the Hellenistic fragments), clearly recognizable by their features and attributes: some Egyptianising figurines (Isis and Harpocrates, “Baubo”, Harpocrates, Bes and *Ptah-Pataikos*),¹⁴ and few Greek-type gods, related to the pleasures of daily life and the care for human reproduction (wine, music, love,

fertility, nature, motherhood and childhood).¹⁵

On the other hand, many figurines depict common people (94,6% of the Hellenistic fragments), worshippers participating in rituals, ceremonies and cult performances of the sanctuary: musicians and dancers, pairs of lovers, mothers and children, draped men and veiled women, many infants and youngsters.

3. The Hellenistic figurines representing women and children: numbers and typologies

Although the Hellenistic typologies attested in Kharayeb are well known in other centers around the Mediterranean (fig. 1), the rate of women and children here is really striking: women are represented at least by 3'672 fragments (22,8% of the Hellenistic fragments), children by 5'624 (35% of the Hellenistic fragments) (fig. 3).

Beside the social representation of well-dressed women, draped, often completely wrapped in a mantle and with a fan – like some figurines from Boeotia (end of 4th-early 3rd cent. BCE) –,¹⁶ many depict female participants to rituals and religious performances: they play an instrument or dance, and hold baskets, jugs or *hydriai* like male amphoras and jugs bearer.

The terracotta figurines of *hydrophoroi*, a widespread Classical and Hellenistic typology found in many cult places, mostly in the East and Asia Minor,¹⁷ are an integral part of our

14 The patterns of the Egyptianising figurines are mostly inspired by the Alexandrian productions and sometimes present a local re-elaboration; Castiglione, 2019.

15 These divine figurines represent exclusively Hellenistic gods of the Greek *pantheon*, whose iconographies have been invented and elaborated in Hellenic contexts. The spheres of influence of these gods are certainly similar to those of local ones like Astarte and Eshmun, for example; cf. Apicella, 2006; Garbati, 2010.

16 Besques, 1971-1972, p. 21-27, pl. 17; Besques, 1994, p. 72-73, p. 75 (Tanagra).

17 On the diffusion of *hydrophoroi* around the Mediterranean (e.g. Tegea, Corinth, Boeotia – Thebes and Orchomenos –, Kos, Samos, Iasos, Caria, Palestine, Cyprus, Egypt, Crete), see: Erlich and Kloner, 2008, p. 34; Kozłowski, 2015. See Karapanagiotou and Leventi, 2015 (Tegea); Merker, 2000, p. 38-42 (Classical period), p. 129 (Hellenistic period), H49, pl. 27 (Corinth); Berti, 2015 (Iasos); Karlsson, 2015 (Labraunda, Caria); Erlich and Kloner, 2008, p. 34, no 88-89, pl. 17; Erlich,

semantic system. They were linked with daily life activities, cult performances or human and natural fertility,¹⁸ and also connected to religious practices associated firstly with a more general female and *kourotrophos* cult, then with those of Demeter and Kore or other gods.¹⁹ In the original Greek contexts, these figurines speak about religious habits and offerings in the sanctuary, and a similar connection with rituals can also be proposed for their use in our cult place, as we explain below.

Regarding the children, despite the lack of information from ancient sources, the iconographic types from Kharayeb allow us to suggest that they refer to aspects of their lives, customs and actions (fig. 4). The division into age groups proposed in the following paragraphs (infants, young children and older youngsters)²⁰ combines two kinds of criteria: the characteristics of their appearance (body proportions, clothes, hairstyle, stance) and the type of action performed, both compared with other sources.

Young males and females imitate adults and take part in the socializing life of the sanctuary. They are involved in different activities, including rituals and offerings: some boys wear a stole, a typical garment of cult attendants (0,2% of the Hellenistic fragments = 0,7% of the children),²¹ or, dressed in a tunic, carry fruit offerings (0,6% of the Hellenistic fragments = 1,8% of the children); males and females offer animals, like the *kriophoroi*, or play with birds (ducks, doves, pigeons and roosters; 2,1% of the Hellenistic fragments = 6% of the children).

In Greek or Hellenized contexts, children were often shown with or playing with small animals in different media (terracotta, statuary, vase painting). In the sanctuaries, birds are the commonest animals probably because they belonged to privileged markers of youth stressed by their connection to divine guardians (Aphrodite, Artemis) as well as to fertility rituals.²² A very relevant parallel for our figurines is the Hellenistic children's frieze in the sanctuary of Eshmun at Bostan esh-Sheikh, near Sidon, where youngsters are represented together with animals (birds and dogs) and are involved in many activities probably linked to festivals or rituals.²³

The patterns and the moulds used in the production of the Hellenistic terracottas found in Kharayeb have a clear Hellenic inspiration, as the comparisons with Greek literary and iconographic sources (stelae, statues, vases) confirm. Jessica Nitschke recently pointed out that “determining cultural provenance of a motif does not in itself explain what meaning it has in the new context, or why certain motifs were chosen while others were rejected. Clearly the

2016 (Palestine, with references to Cyprus and Egypt); Kassab Tezgör, 2007, p. 194, no 260, pl. 78c (Alexandria). For female figurines holding *hydriai* and males amphoras bearer from Crete: Besques, 1971-1972, p. 62, pl. 77b; p. 63, pl. 80d.

18 They could reflect the status of young girls or citizens' wives or the use of water as a part of ritual purifications. Otherwise, the connection with fertility refers to the ritual bathing of brides.

19 The *hydrophoroi* from Thebes (Archaeological Museum of Thebes), Kos (Archaeological Museum of Kos), and Samos (Archaeological Museum of Pythagorion) were found in sanctuaries dedicated to Demeter. Those from Orchomenos, also displayed in the Archaeological Museum of Thebes, were votive offerings in the sanctuary of the 'Chthonic Deities'. All these materials are not published.

20 Cf. Beaumont, 2003, p. 75-77.

21 Cf. Oggiano, 2013.

22 Cf. Minunno, 2006.

23 Will, 1985, p. 122-124; Stucky, 1997 and 2005, p. 172-181, pls. 19-23.

Phoenicians were selective, and had good reasons for picking certain motifs while rejecting others”.²⁴ So, if those Hellenic patterns were widely distributed in the Mediterranean, the selection of the types reflects their reception and influence on local collective or individual needs in this particular area of Hellenistic Phoenicia.²⁵

Our study will thus take into account the complex relationship between the original artistic styles and their transmission, re-elaboration and impact on Phoenician culture, in order to refine our understanding on the influence of the Greek lifestyle in this region.²⁶

4. Performing games and being a child in the cult place (c. 2-4 years of age)

One very peculiar feature of the Kharayeb’s assemblage is the great number of figurines representing children playing with birds and dogs, the favorite pets both for males and females (3% of the Hellenistic fragments = 8,5% of the children). Such percentage is not very common in terracottas. It is found only in two groups of different materials: the marble statues, so-called temple-boys, from the sanctuary of Bostan esh-Sheikh, 3 km far from Sidon, and the terracotta figurines from Myrina.

The age group discussed here (c. 2-4 years old) has been identified thanks to the infantile appearance and proportions of the figurines as well as to their very simple activities linked to the world of play. Thus, children included in this category are generally characterized by a chubby body; boys are dressed in a tunic or naked, with or without mantel, and they often have a long hairdo; little girls wear a belted, sleeveless *chiton*. They all play with animals and sometimes feed and/or tease them with a bunch of grapes.

4.1. Play with birds

Many figurines depict prepubescent children holding and playing with birds: male children in a short tunic walk holding the neck of a goose; naked boys in a mantle hold a duck and play with it; little girls with a belted, sleeveless *chiton* play with a dove.

These images are found in other archaeological contexts: male and female children play with roosters in Eretria, Troy, and Myrina,²⁷ with birds in Boeotia (Thebes), Myrina, and Crimea, and a little girl sits with a bird in Alexandria.²⁸

At least one example of the boys with a goose is inspired by a famous Greek iconographic model: the much-copied group of a naked, chubby baby boy grappling playfully with a large goose almost his own size, recalls the Boethos’ statue dating to the end of the 3rd century BCE

24 Nitschke, 2015.

25 Cf. Lancellotti, 2003; Oggiano, 2015a and 2015b. On the connections between the terracotta figurines found in Kharayeb and the typologies produced and widespread in Alexandria, see Castiglione, 2019.

26 Cf. Nitschke, 2007; 2011; 2013; 2015. On the many aspects related to the culture of Hellenistic Phoenicia, see Bonnet, 2015a.

27 Mollard-Besques, 1963, p. 134, pls. 162c and 162f (Myrina); Besques, 1971-1972, p. 64, pl. 83a (Eretria); Burr Thompson, 1963, p. 138-139, no 284 (Troy).

28 Pisani, 2012 (Boeotia); Mollard-Besques, 1963, p. 133-134 (Myrina); Besques, 1971-1972, p. 58, pl. 69d (Crimea).

(fig. 5).²⁹ Although we cannot claim that the portrait aimed at depicting a specific child, it does nevertheless express a significant degree of feelings for childhood, and as such constitutes an example of pathos-imbued Hellenistic genre of child. A terracotta from Tarsus and a very similar one from Patara represent a variant of this pattern: a sitting little boy is depicted strangling a goose.³⁰ This kind of agonistic activity evokes Heracles' childhood.

Many other figurines from Kharayeb show boys standing, with a short tunic or naked with a mantle, feeding and/or teasing pigeons or doves with a bunch of grapes (fig. 6). This motif was created in Boeotia in the early 5th century BCE and widespread in the central-eastern Mediterranean, in sanctuaries dedicated to female deities as well as in the tombs of Myrina and in some domestic contexts at Priene and Delos.³¹

Other children, sitting or standing, wearing a short tunic or just a mantle or naked, are depicted feeding and/or teasing ducks or cocks with a bunch of grapes.³² The pair of child and cock, a favourite pet, is well known on Attic *choes* and gravestones. The animal had an erotic meaning as a lovers' gift in Greece,³³ and in Hellenic sanctuaries its presence could also allude to Asklepios³⁴ and to the first hair cut at the age of four, when children dedicated the strand of hair with a cock and some sweets.³⁵

4.2. Play with dogs

Play with the dog, the pet *par excellence*, is a very important part of childhood activities. In Kharayeb many figurines represent children with the Maltese dog which was a close companion and a double of the child, as evidenced by its regular presence on grave stelae, Attic *choes* and in youngsters' statues.³⁶ The animal is generally depicted with a long coat, jumping and balancing itself on its hind legs, the tail curling over its back. Sometimes the child teases the dog with a bunch of grapes, a fruit appreciated by the animal, in order to train it and maybe to stimulate a higher jump.³⁷ These figurines can be compared with Hellenistic

29 On the statue and its sculptor: Plin. *NH* 34, 84. Cf. Herodas, *Mim.* 4, 30-34.

30 Besques, 1971-1972, p. 296, pl. 370b (Tarsus); Işin 2007, p. 72-73, p. 156 (Patara).

31 Cf. Mathieux, 2015, in part. p. 250. We can also add a terracotta of a little girl with grapes found in Smyrna.

32 Cf. the infant figurines with grapes and ducks from Myrina; Mollard-Besques, 1963, p. 133, pls. 161a-f, 162b, 167d.

33 The cock was an erotic symbol, a love-gift in the hands of the desired youth, like in the Ganymede myth; cf. Neils and Oakley, 2003b, p. 282, n° 94; Kathariou, 2006.

34 Cf. Minunno, 2006, p. 114.

35 Cf. Pisani, 2012, p. 376, fig. 4, 379.

36 On the importance of dogs in children's education, see Vespa, 2019b. For the Maltese dog in literary sources and archaeological material, see Cinaglia, 2012. Cf. Neils and Oakley, 2003c, p. 307, n° 124 (Attic marble gravestone of a young girl with a Maltese dog); p. 285, no 95 (Attic red-figure *chous* showing a boy with a dog). Among the sculptures, cf. the Late Hellenistic torso of a small sepulchral statue of a boy holding a Maltese dog in his arms, found in the western area of the ancient necropolis of Rhodes (Ai Yannis) and now displayed in the Archaeological Museum of Rhodes (unpublished), as well as the so-called temple-boys from the sanctuary of Eshmun near Sidon; Stucky, 1993, p. 86, no 113, pl. 28.

37 Cf. the figurines from Myrina, some stelae from Smyrna and some *choes* from Athens and Eretria; Mathieux, 2015, p. 247 and p. 260, fig. 2; p. 248-249 and p. 261, fig. 5; p. 251 and p. 262, figs. 7-8,

terracottas from other sites: Athens, Boeotia, Olynthus (Chalcidice), Delos, Kos, Samos, Myrina, Troy, Kilia (Troad), Crimea, Alexandria and Cyprus.³⁸ The diffusion of this particular dog species on paintings, reliefs and as clay toys in regions outside Greece, may allude to the role of these animals in ancient families, which may have accompanied the Greek settlers.

In Kharayeb some figurines mix the image of the sitting naked chubby child holding a duck and stroking a Maltese dog. This synthetic combination of two different situations is also attested on prepubescent children tombstones from ancient Macedonia.³⁹

5. Transition from childhood to adolescence (c. 5-14 years of age)

Individuals who remained children forever – like Eros or Adonis – were dangerous and subversive, while immortal and mortal children were expected to grow into adult capacities and roles.⁴⁰

In this perspective, some figurines from Kharayeb show activities probably linked to a transitional phase from childhood to adolescence. In this age group (c. 5-14 years old) are included terracottas of young children and older youngsters, also identified thanks to the comparison with other kinds of sources. For a better understanding, we will detail the data considered in this classification.

Although some terracottas have a childish appearance, similar to those examined in the previous group – body proportions, clothes, hairdos and stance –, their interpretation as relevant examples of a liminal phase at the end of the childhood is associated with the identification of the performed actions. This is the case of children saving a bunch of grapes from a bird or holding a ball in the right hand, or making a fruit's offering.

Nevertheless, the figurines playing and training a dog with a ball or experiencing the many aspects of education (sport, music, theatre and school) have been included in this phase for the combination of their activities, the physical characteristics and their clothes (the slim body, the short hair and the voluminous *himation* for boys; the long sleeveless *chiton* or the long-belted *chiton* with sleeves and a *himation* for girls).

10. Cf. Cinaglia, 2012, p. 119-120.

38 Besques, 1971-1972, p. 35, pl. 43e; Pisani, 2016, p. 200 and p. 207, fig. 3 (Boeotia); Robinson, 1952, p. 215-216, pl. 92 (Olynthus); Mollard-Besques, 1963, p. 134, pls. 163a-c, 163f and 164f (Myrina); Burr Thompson, 1963, p. 140, no 287 (Troy); for a little girl figurine from Crimea: Besques, 1971-1972, p. 58, pl. 69a. A terracotta figurine from Kos (Archaeological Museum of Kos) shows a standing child in partial nudity, with a mantle, holding and embracing his beloved dog. The figurines from Samos, found in the *Heraion* or in other contexts (Archaeological Museums of Samos-Vathi and Pythagorion), present two iconographic types: children standing in a long tunic, with a heavy mantle and sometimes a thick wreath, while playing with a Maltese dog jumping on their right side; children sitting on a rock, in partial nudity and with a mantle, holding a Maltese dog on his right hand, which is licking his face. The figurines from Kos and Samos are unpublished.

39 Kalaitzi, 2010.

40 Cf. Golden, 2003, p. 14.

5.1. *Growing up with the rules*

Some figurines represent children saving a bunch of grapes from a possible duck (fig. 7). This image recalls a similar famous example from Myrina, where the bird is not a duck but a rooster. Such an iconography was mostly popular in Asia Minor, as depicted on a gravestone from Smyrna,⁴¹ and the whole composition reminds of the well-known terracotta groups with a more explicit cockfight.⁴² As Marco Vespa recently demonstrated, this activity provided pleasure for youth of all ages and, by contrast with the animal's behavior, trained the control of pugnacious impulses and offered a model for a correct *paideia*.⁴³ Négune Mathieux also interpreted the scene of grapes' protection as a sort of liminal phase for the childhood; the game would represent a form of rite of passage displaying the social training of young boys.⁴⁴ She reflected on the contrast between adults and animals evoked by the bunch of grapes and the birds: it implies that the child would abandon his wild nature when getting older, unlike the animals picking the grapes. Growing up meant leaving the game itself in order to adopt the behavior of a young boy and later of a good citizen.

5.2. *From ball play to fruit offering*

Another activity halfway between childhood and an older age is shown by young boys standing in partial nudity, with a mantle only, training their Maltese dog flinging a ball (0,9% of the Hellenistic fragments = 2,5% of the children). The dog included in early childhood play is here involved in athletic activities (fig. 8).⁴⁵

In the Greek world, many depictions refer to a great variety of ball games.⁴⁶ A bronze statuette of a boy from the sanctuary of Zeus in Dodona (late 4th-early 3rd cent. BCE) refers to playing activities connected to the age of transition from boyhood to adolescence; the ball-player, between 5 and 8 years old, holds a leather ball in the right hand.⁴⁷ He has long curly hair in plaits, alluding to the time before the ceremonial haircut marking his transition from childhood to adolescence, at the age of fourteen.⁴⁸ The comparison of this particular characteristic allows us to hypothesize that our figurines represent some youngsters older than the child found in Dodona, as evident from their shorter hairdos.

41 Mathieux, 2015, p. 248 and p. 261, fig. 4 (terracotta figurine); p. 257 and p. 263, fig. 13 (stele). Cf. Mollard-Besques, 1963, p. 134, pl. 162f.

42 Cf. Burr Thompson, 1963, p. 138-139, n° 284 (Troy); Neils and Oakley, 2003b, p. 282, n° 94 (terracotta figurine with children at a cockfight, from Amisos). On the cockfights, see Kathariou, 2006.

43 Cf. Vespa, 2019a.

44 Cf. Mathieux, 2015, esp. p. 252.

45 Cf. Cinaglia, 2012.

46 See the ball games described by Pollux, *Onomasticon*; Costanza, 2019. Cf. three Late Hellenistic figurines from the Marmaroto necropolis in Kos, showing male adolescents holding a ball on their raised right hand (Archaeological Museum of Kos, unpublished).

47 Bobou, 2015, p. 75-76; Giovanopoulou, 2019; Dasen, 2020, fig. 2. See a terracotta figurine from Corinth (3rd-early 2nd cent. BCE), depicting a naked boy in a similar pose (Besques, 1971-1972, p. 54, pl. 63c; Hasselin Rous, 2019, p. 57, fig. 2). On the recommendation of ball games for health, see A. Pietrobelli in this volume.

48 On the ritual cutting of the boy's hair, see Neils, 2003, p. 145 and p. 153.

In Kharayeb other male figurines with balls are characterized by a peculiar attitude. The boys are standing in partial nudity, wearing a mantle only, the right arm alongside the bust, holding a ball in the right hand (fig. 9). Some terracottas of young boys dressed in a short tunic and a mantle, but with a similar pose, are attested at Myrina, while a figurine of a nude boy with a mantle on his left shoulder, holding with the right hand a ball resting on his belly, has been found in a grave of the Marmaroto necropolis in Kos.⁴⁹ This iconography also recurs in sculpture, like the statue of a standing boy wearing a *himation* and holding, in his left hand, a ball against his stomach, from the sanctuary of Asklepios at Piraeus (early 2nd cent. BCE).⁵⁰ In Kalymnos, a Hellenistic marble statue found in a deposit of sculptures near the sanctuary of Apollo Dalios offers another parallel: a naked boy holds a ball in his left hand, with curly hair and a forelock in the central part of the head, a hairstyle similar to the Kharayeb's figurines too.⁵¹

In these cases, as well, despite the childish physical appearance – the chubby body and the long hair – the meaningful gesture of holding a ball in the hand reveals the inclusion in the age group of the young children. This attitude can be related to an epigram by Leonidas from Taras (c. 300-250 BCE). The poet describes how the young boy Philocles offered to Hermes the toys of his boyhood: his castanets, the knucklebones, his spinning-top and his ball.⁵² Thus, the terracottas from Kharayeb most likely allude to the ball's offering in the sanctuary. This hypothesis seems to be supported by male figurines from Myrina holding in the right hand the ball and in the left hand an object interpreted as a little ship or a more generic child toy.⁵³

In a similar semantic system relating to rites of passage to adolescence, we propose to consider too the figurines of young children holding fruit as performing an offering. This type is found in other contexts, such as Myrina.⁵⁴ The boys generally carry apples, objects with a metaphoric meaning related to mutual relationships and love affairs, as Véronique Dasen has convincingly pointed out.⁵⁵ Thus, our figurines could be interpreted as referring to rite of passage of young boys between puberty and adulthood, with erotic connotations, if we consider the lifted dress unveiling the genital area.

We can corroborate these suggestions with material found in the sanctuary of Bostan esh-Sheikh. The place, founded in the early 6th century BCE, was famous for religious practices connected to children prophylaxis, medicine and healing, which involved water and sacred

49 Mollard-Besques, 1963, p. 129, pls. 155a and 155c, p. 130, pl. 156d (Myrina). The figurine from Kos is displayed in the Archaeological Museum of Kos (unpublished).

50 Bobou, 2015, p. 139, no 46: the statue is attributed to the age group from 2 to 5 years.

51 Archaeological Museum of Kalymnos, Pothia (unpublished).

52 *The Greek Anthology*, 6, 309 (Leonidas): “To Hermes Philocles here hands up these toys of his boyhood: his noiseless ball, this lively boxwood rattle, his knuckle-bones he had such a mania for, and his spinning-top” (transl. W. R. Paton, Loeb). Cf. Dasen, 2013, p. 9. Generally, before wedding and usually at the age of fourteen or fifteen, girls dedicated to gods their toys (e.g. dolls, tambourine and ball); cf. *The Greek Anthology*, 6, 280; Neils, 2003, p. 152.

53 Mollard-Besques, 1963, p. 129, pls. 155a and 155c (the figurine 155b holds the toy only).

54 Mollard-Besques, 1963, p. 132, pls. 159a and 159c. Cf. the small headless Late Hellenistic statue of a standing boy from 2 to 5 years depicted in the same attitude from the quarries of San Giovanni, in the western area of the ancient necropolis of Rhodes, Ai Yannis; Bobou, 2015, p. 156, no 102.

55 Dasen, 2016 and 2018a. Cf. *The Greek Anthology*, 5, 80 and 5, 214.

basins. A few terracottas of children and roosters were discovered, figurines of protective deities like Harpocrates and Bes,⁵⁶ and marble statues representing youngsters playing with birds, turtles, balls or astragali. In the two cult places, many astragali and glass counters were found too.⁵⁷ Knucklebones were used for children's games and entertainment, and in religious contexts;⁵⁸ they could represent the dedications of playthings to a deity by boys and girls on the occasion of coming of age, before wedding or at the end of the childhood.⁵⁹

The finds from Bostan esh-Sheikh and those from Kharayeb thus let us infer that children were here involved in rituals and/or rites of passage.

5.3. Education for boys and girls: sport, music, theatre and school (c. 7-14 years of age)

A prepubescent child was placed in the process of education and incorporation into the world of adults by the carefree world of play, athletic and music training. Beside athletic and military training, intellectual education (philosophical and scientific) was also provided. The famous school scene depicted on the Attic red-figure *kylix* signed by Douris (490-480 BCE) resumes well all these fields of knowledge (athletics, music and grammar).⁶⁰ The in-depth analysis of these particular aspects surely will offer food for thought on the question of Greek-style culture and education in Hellenistic Phoenicia, generally accepted for coastal and urban centers.⁶¹

Physical exercise was essential in the basic education of *ephebes*, whose sound and healthy body was an important feature of their life. Greek boys were expected to go to the *gymnasium* at about the age of 12-14 years old, exercising naked and cleaning their sweaty bodies by applying oil and scraping it off with a strigil.⁶² In Kharayeb, a few figurines of boys are depicted with strigil and *alabastra* (0,03% of the Hellenistic fragments = 0,09% of the children), paralleled in a terracotta found at Myrina, depicting a child with the strigil.⁶³ While historical and literary sources strongly support both the presence of *gymnasia*⁶⁴ and the institution of Olympic games in the region,⁶⁵ as well as the successful competitions of

56 Ganzmann *et al.*, 1987.

57 On the sanctuary in Bostan esh-Sheikh, see Dunand, 1978; Ganzmann *et al.*, 1987; Stucky, 1991 and 1997; Lancellotti, 2003, p. 347; Minunno, 2006. The association of glass beads and glass knucklebones recurs also in Hellenistic children's tombs; cf. the unpublished material from the Western Cemetery of the ancient city of Samos (Archaeological Museums of Pythagorion).

58 Cf. Carè, 2013.

59 Cf. Neils and Oakley, 2003b, p. 279, no 88-90.

60 Cf. Neils and Oakley, 2003a, p. 244-246, no 44.

61 Cf. Bonnet, 2015a.

62 Cf. Neils and Oakley, 2003a, p. 244.

63 Mollard-Besques, 1963, p. 132, pl. 159e.

64 The book 2 of Maccabees (4.7-15) mentions a *gymnasium* in Jerusalem (c. 174 BCE), some specific activities and terms such as *ephebes*, the *petasos* hat and sports, like discus; cf. Kennel, 2005. A bilingual inscription from Arados (25/4 BCE) testifies the presence of a *gymnasium* in this center; Bonnet, 2015a, p. 128-131. On the *gymnasium* as a symbolic place for the Hellenized education and the status of the city, see Couvenhes and Heller, 2006.

65 Festival games are known in Tyre: Alexander the Great performed some rites including athletic games in the precinct of the temple of Heracles/Melqart, a relay torch-race, some musical and

Phoenicians in contests abroad,⁶⁶ few archaeological sources complement our athletic images. We can consider a few marble statues of youngsters from the sanctuary of Eshmun at Bostan esh-Sheikh, possibly interpreted as athletes,⁶⁷ fragments of Panathenaic amphorae found in the same context (second half of the 4th century BCE)⁶⁸ and the ruins of a partially excavated *stadium* at Amrit, dubiously dated in the Hellenistic period.⁶⁹ Thus, the iconography of our terracotta figurines invites to reflect whether such images could be related to a real athletic training, variously attested in the region, or to the ambition to become an accomplished athlete, rather than to a simple aesthetic choice.

Music was also regarded as very important for reaching the status of *polites*, well-educated citizen. Choral singing and dancing were central in religious practices.⁷⁰ In *Protagoras*, Plato requires that children:

“learn to play the harp... and they [i.e. the music-masters] insist on familiarizing the boys’ souls with the rhythms and scales, that they may gain in gentleness, and by advancing in rhythmic and harmonic grace may be efficient in speech and action; for the whole of man’s life requires the graces of rhythm and harmony”.⁷¹

Many figurines from Kharayeb represent young boys and girls both dancing and/or playing one of the many instruments: syrinx, trigon, tambourine, kithara, lyre and maybe harp (0,8% of the Hellenistic fragments = 2,2% of the children). These images may refer to their participation in rituals but can also testify an aspect of their education.

The theatre was another fundamental part of the Greek *paideia* and an epigram of Asclepiades may explain the possible link between youngsters, education and theatre, as he mentions the offering of a comic mask after a boys’ contest.⁷² In Kharayeb, only two terracottas depict youngsters holding a mask,⁷³ while few other figurines represent comic actors and grotesques, but not necessarily young people (0,3% of the Hellenistic fragments).

theatrical performances; Arr., *Anab.*, 2.24, 3.6.1; Diod. Sic., 17.46; Plut., *Alexander*, 29. By the time of Antiochos IV games of some sort were being held every five years (2 *Macc.* 4.18; cf. Nitschke, 2007, p. 167) as well as the Olympic games dedicated to Heracles around 170 BCE (4 *Macc.* 4.20).

66 Phoenicians were successful in boxing competitions at Delos, horse races in the *Panathenaia* and chariot-races in the Nemean games. See e.g. the honorific inscription dedicated by Sidonians to Diotimos (c. 200 BCE), which attests his victory in the chariot-race of the Nemean games; Nitschke, 2007, p. 167-168; Bonnet, 2015a, p. 260-265; Bonnet, 2015b, p. 185-186; Bonnet, 2018, p. 54-56.

67 Cf. Stucky, 1993, p. 38-39.

68 Bentz, 1998, p. 185, n° 4.216-4.218, p. 193, n° 4.361 and n° 4.364, p. 226.

69 Nitschke, 2007, p. 49 and p.183-184.

70 On the role of the music performances in Hellenistic shrines, see Queyrel, 1988.

71 Plato, *Protagoras*, 326a-b (transl. W. R. M. Lamb, Loeb).

72 *The Greek Anthology*, 6, 308 (Asclepiades): “Connarus, on winning the boys’ contest, since he wrote such a pretty hand, received eighty knuckle-bones, and in gratitude to the Muses he hung me up here, the comic mask of old Chares, amid the applause of the boys” (transl. W. R. Paton, Loeb). Cf. Todisco, 2005; Pisani, 2012, p. 382 and note 61.

73 The figurines represent two young boys naked with a mantle, holding a bearded head or a mask in the left hand; Chéhab, 1951-1952, p. 75-76 n° x. Differently, a young couple with a mask has been interpreted as Eros and Psyche; Chéhab, 1951-1952, p. 29 n° f; Chéhab, 1953-1954, pl. XIV, 3. Cf. Erlich and Kloner, 2008, p. 39-41, no 108-109, pl. 21.

This very scanty number is not surely representative of a children and youngsters' activity, but it suggests anyway an unusual practice among the young people attending the sanctuary. Therefore, such a lack of information confirms that the rituals performed in Kharayeb involved only children in transition from childhood to adolescence, leaving aside the connection to adulthood and the role of citizen, to whom the theatre prepared.⁷⁴

The basic curriculum for the first degree of children education, beginning at age of seven, also included writing, reading, recitation and arithmetic, along with rhetoric.⁷⁵ In Hellenistic times, education was widespread both in formal schools and in informal gathering places. The socializing importance of school and festivals is well evidenced in Kharayeb, where numerous schooling scenes have been found: they include seated and standing male figurines as well as seated female terracottas (2% of the Hellenistic fragments = 5,7% of the children) (fig. 10).

The types illustrate the different phases of schooling of male children: the younger boys are seated, with a tablet set upon their knees, and the older boys are standing, holding a tablet set or a papyrus scroll.

The seated pupils have plump faces and bodies with clear features of childhood, and their hair is generally arranged with a plait running back from the middle of the forehead.⁷⁶ They wear a tunic or they are draped in a voluminous *himation* leaving the upper part of the chest bare. They are represented carefully writing or reading on a diptych upon their knees. Parallels of such scenes are found in a broad geographical area (i.e. Athens, Boeotia – Thebes and Tanagra –, Euboea – Eretria and Amarynthos –, Mysia – Parion –, Myrina, Magnesia, Tarsus).⁷⁷

The standing male figurines hold a papyrus scroll or a diptych; they represent older boys, recognizable by the modeling of the body, the shorter hair and the overall hieratic pose, usually enveloped in a *himation*. The type with the papyrus scroll has no parallels, except for a figurine of a seated boy found in Boeotia, with a papyrus scroll in the left hand and his lower body wrapped in mantle.⁷⁸ The standing boy with the tablet set is also not very widespread: a mould of a standing male pupil wearing a mantle and holding the writing tablet with his left arm has been discovered at Maresha,⁷⁹ a figurine of a probable standing schoolboy comes from Tel Anafa,⁸⁰ while some standing pupils – but girls – have been found at Myrina and Alexandria.⁸¹

74 Cf. the statuettes of theatrical subjects found in some burials of children, who died at an age when they were preparing to participate with adults in the life of the theater, intended to emphasize the transition from childhood to maturity. See Ferruzza, 2016, p. 91-92.

75 Cf. Neils and Oakley, 2003a, p. 244; Marrou, 2016. On the curriculum of young school children, see also E. Dickey in this volume.

76 Considering the cutting of the boy's hair at the age of fourteen (cf. Neils, 2003, p. 145 and p. 153), we can suppose that our seated figurines represent pupils under fourteen years old.

77 Pisani, 2016, p. 199 (Thebes, with references to Athens and Tanagra); Pisani, 2012, p. 379-381 and fig. 9 (Thebes); Benissi, 2019 (Amarynthos, with references to other geographical areas); Kozanlı, 2015, p. 388 and p. 396, fig. 7 (Parion); Besques, 1971-1972, p. 267, pl. 370i (Tarsus). Some terracottas from Eretria are displayed in the Archaeological Museum of Eretria (unpublished).

78 Besques, 1971-1972, p. 35, pl. 43c.

79 Erlich and Kloner, 2008, p. 38, no 101, pl. 19.

80 Erlich, 2018, p. 240, no TF 20.

81 Mollard-Besques, 1963, p. 135, pl. 165d (Myrina); Kassab Tezgör, 2007, p. 182 no 238-239, pl. 71c-d (Alexandria); Nenna, 2012, p. 274-275 and fig. 4b (Alexandria).

Figurines of schoolgirls are rarer in Kharayeb. They generally wear a tunic or a long sleeveless *chiton*, and sometimes a long-belted *chiton* with sleeves and a *himation*. They sit on a cubic block or often on a four legs bench, derived from the *diphros*,⁸² and hold a diptych on their lap. Unlike boys, girls and young women are depicted in the process of reading rather than writing. This type has some parallels in Argos, Boeotia, Euboea – Eretria and Amarynthos –, Myrina, Alexandria and Maresha.⁸³ In Eretria and Alexandria, the gender percentage found in Kharayeb is inverted: the female figurines with a *diptych* in their lap are very popular, while the boy figurines are found in a smaller number.⁸⁴

As for athletic training or theatrical performances, no data allows us to surely ascertain the worshippers' education either in the hinterland of our sanctuary,⁸⁵ or in the close Tyre, where some Greek-style schools may have existed.⁸⁶ However Greek-speaking literary personalities are well known in Late Hellenistic Phoenicia, such as Antipater and Zenon of Sidon or Meleager of Gadara, although there is no evidence about their education in the region.⁸⁷ Thus, if terracottas cannot provide unquestionable information on the worshippers' schooling, the deliberate selection of such a specific iconography of learning is certainly a meaningful sign of an individual experience, either real or hoped for.

It is well known that in the Hellenistic period school education was widespread for both boys and girls, but the pupils from Kharayeb reveal a deeper gender differentiation. The presence of girls and young women suggests that, in southern Phoenicia, female primary school education also consisted in learning to read like their male age-mates. However, the figurines indicate that writing skills, both with stylus and wax tablet or with ink and papyrus scroll, were reserved to boys only. The choice, however, may distort the reality. The Hellenistic hoard of a young woman found in the not far site of Tel Kedesh, offers a different picture: together with a hairpin, an Eros terracotta figurine and some glass astragals and gaming pieces, a writing paraphernalia including a stylus and an inkwell was discovered.⁸⁸

82 Kassab Tezgör, 2007, p. 42, no 3.

83 Besques, 1971-1972, p. 35, pl. 43a (Boeotia, with references to Argos); Chidiroglou, 2015, p. 97-98 and p. 105, fig. 19 (Eretria); Benissi, 2019 (Amarynthos, with references to other geographical areas); Mollard-Besques, 1963, p. 111-112, pls. 134c-d and 134f (Myrina); Breccia, 1912, p. 129-130, no 405 and pl. LXX, 188, p. 149-150, no 481-482 and pl. LXXIII, 223; Kassab Tezgör, 2007, p. 41-42, n° 3 and pls. 5b and 13c, p. 190-191, no 253 and pl. 77a, p. 201, no 269 and pl. 80c; Nenna, 2012, p. 274-275, fig. 3 (Alexandria); Erlich, 2019, p. 227-228, fig. 13.5 (Maresha. "One unique figurine shows two pupils seated on a bench with their writing tablets, of which only the girl survived (the other might have been a boy?) ... According to the fabric this figurine seems to have been imported").

84 Chidiroglou, 2015, p. 97 (Eretria). The few percentages attested in Alexandria are due to their absence in the publications; Breccia, 1912; Kassab Tezgör, 2007.

85 Cf. Oggiano, 2015a, p. 518.

86 Cf. Oggiano, 2015b, p. 244.

87 Nitschke, 2007, p. 170-171. On the Greek scholarly life in Palestine during the Hellenistic period, see Geiger, 2014.

88 Erlich, 2017.

Conclusion

This abundant material provides new insights about the cult and the rituals attested in Kharayeb, as well as about the social roles, the age classes and sex differentiation of the people moving in the sanctuary.

Some scholars have tried to define the god worshipped thanks to the assemblage of figurines: Maria Grazia Lancellotti criticized the definition of “mystères ésotériques” proposed by Maurice Chéhab and Ibrahim Kaoukabani. She argued that the shrine was most likely dedicated to healing cults open to all, in particular to children, as in the case of the sanctuary of Eshmun at Bostan esh-Sheikh. This would explain the high number of youngsters’ figurines, considering that the attention towards childhood was specific to healing cults.⁸⁹ The children may have spent a period of time in the sanctuary to observe prophylaxis and/or healing treatments, even if no archaeological evidences can confirm this hypothesis.

Whoever the god(s) was, he/she was certainly linked to human fertility, healing, motherhood, childhood and puberty, as the many female figurines, *hydrophoroi*, *kourotrophoi*, youngsters and birds suggest. At least in Greek or Hellenized contexts, also the few images of deities documented by the terracottas found in our sanctuary head in the same direction:⁹⁰ Isis, Bes,⁹¹ *Ptah-Pataikos*,⁹² Harpocrates,⁹³ “Baubo”,⁹⁴ as well as Heracles,⁹⁵ Dionysus,⁹⁶ Apollo,⁹⁷ Artemis,⁹⁸ Hermes,⁹⁹ Demeter, Aphrodite and Eros.

The presence of other figurines and objects complete this panorama: bunches of grapes, astragali, a probable turtle and the many ‘mantle dancers’, alluding to the movement of a

89 Lancellotti, 2003; Oggiano, 2015a.

90 In addition to the mentioned deities, we have to notice the presence of monkeys, referring to the children life protection with the role of wet nurse (Bellia, 2014, p. 60), and/or baboons, alluding to the condition of limen attributed to the dead fetus (Dasen, 2015, p. 211).

91 Bes was a guardian against the bad souls, the patron of births and children in general; Lancellotti, 2003, p. 350 and p. 356.

92 *Ptah-Pataikos* was connected to the fetus. See Dasen, 2015, p. 147-148.

93 Harpocrates was a symbol of childhood in Greco-Roman Egypt; Bonnet, 2015a, p. 249.

94 “Baubo” was important for female sexuality and fertility (Dasen, 2015, p. 102-103) and she was a mythical example of wet nurse (Bellia, 2014, p. 58-59).

95 Omphale/Heracles had prophylaxis value. Furthermore, Heracles with his infancy and childhood summarized all the troubles of the newborn children, and he was also connected with a funerary dimension; Bonnet, 2015a, p. 249.

96 Dionysus was linked to the transition from childhood to puberty and to the death as well. See Bonnet, 2015a, p. 249.

97 Apollo, the *kouros* god *par excellence*, was the guide for youngsters during passages of age and he was often called *kourotrophos*; Nobili, 2013, p. 157.

98 Artemis was worshipped as *kourotrophos* and protector of the family and all children, regardless of gender. She often coincided with *Eilithyia*, protector of pregnancy and childbirth. She was also associated with girls’ transitions and to critical phases in the lives of women, such as the passage from childhood to puberty and the preparation for marriage and motherhood; Benissi, 2019, p. 211.

99 Hermes was the patron of children and had an important role in their education; cf. Nobili, 2013, p. 157.

spinning-top, always remind Aphrodite, Hermes and Dionysus;¹⁰⁰ birds and cocks are connected to Aphrodite and to the healing cult of Asklepios;¹⁰¹ women holding the *platagé*, a kind of rattle used by adults to quieten babies, are linked to infancy (fig. 11);¹⁰² Silenus recalls the education with the pedagogue.¹⁰³

All these evidences let us infer the existence of rites of passage, similar to those in other areas around the Mediterranean, marking the transition from childhood to puberty and the consequent incorporation into the ranks of adults, differentiated according to gender.

The terracottas representing common people could be used as sources for an anthropological approach, as suggested by Arthur Muller,¹⁰⁴ in order to reconstruct rituals and actions in the sanctuary as well as the characteristics of the social and cultural life in this geographical area. As Agnès Garcia-Ventura and Mireia López-Beltran have pointed out, figurines are not passive objects but can be seen as material culture in motion: they “not only model people or divinities praying or dancing, but also provoke movements and embody practices among the people who observe, touch, or interact with them”.¹⁰⁵ In this sense, a multilayered analysis of our data could provide more than one key of understanding. Our first interpretation considers children with bunches of grapes, balls and pets as images belonging to household and daily life in ancient cities and villages. But these types were found in a specific religious context. On one hand, the local children certainly participated in the ritual life of the shrine, for whom we only have indirect evidences. They share the dressing habits and values of adults, emulating them in offerings, music playing and dancing, that were important elements in religious ceremonies. On the other hand, several sources refer to the children’s life in the sanctuary: they perhaps benefitted of a collective life in its open spaces.¹⁰⁶ Furthermore, figurines depicting athletic activities, theatre and schooling enlarge our information on the adoption of a Greek-style education in Hellenistic southern Phoenicia.

In the Kharayeb’s assemblage, it seems to be possible to classify figurines and their actions on the basis of the various age stages, from children to adolescents, thanks to their activities and physical aspect.¹⁰⁷ Prepubescent boys and girls share some common attributes and gestures, which place them in the world of play, with birds and dogs. At some point, little boys abandon childish objects and attitudes, starting to learn rules, like protecting grapes from the birds, and training their bodies with balls and dogs, maybe frequenting the *gymnasia* or ‘unofficial’ open spaces. Becoming older implies changing entertainments and offering

100 Grapes, astragali, spinning-top and turtle recall Dionysus; cf. Dasen, 2015, p. 302.

101 Whereas the iconography of child with an animal can be seen as a representation of the real life, it is also proper that the figurines of specific animals refer to the deities worshipped: doves to Adonis and Aphrodite, the cock to Asklepios, and the quail to Melqart, for example; cf. Minunno, 2006, p. 114.

102 Bellia, 2014, p. 59-60.

103 Cf. Dasen, 2015, p. 302; Benissi, 2019, p. 210.

104 Muller, 2017-2018.

105 García-Ventura and López-Beltrán, 2010, p. 740.

106 On children’s activities in the sanctuary, see Dasen, 2020 (in press). For an example of children playing in a sanctuary, see Pausanias, 8.23.6-7. Cf. the advice of Plato, *Laws*, 794a.

107 We have a similar differentiation on the basis of age in the sanctuary of Bostan esh-Sheikh; Stucky, 1993, p. 39.

to the god(s) the objects related to previous games, like the ball. Girls do not seem to be included in these actions, but they have an active role in other aspects of ritual and education, such as music and dance. Male youngsters also participate in music and dance, while athletic activities are an exclusive prerogative of boys.

By the age of seven, both boys and girls were assumed to be involved in schooling, as attested elsewhere in the Hellenistic period. Girls are represented reading only, while boys seem to have a more extended education, writing with stylus on wax tablets, as well as on papyrus scrolls with ink.

In conclusion, the terracotta figurines from Kharayeb, with their proximity to the real world and the allusion to Hellenized models, are an important source for understanding and visualizing the life in the sanctuary and nearby centers. They also give voice to women and especially to children and youngsters, who seem to be the main actors and participants in this cult place, where they worshipped the god(s) seeking help on their path towards maturity.

Some last questions are open: did plays/toys for the god(s) aim at securing divine protection for children? Did children play games in the sanctuary during prophylactic treatments or rites of passage, or did they simply enjoy distraction while their parents performed routine rituals? Unfortunately, no unique answer is available, and, for the two last points, we cannot ascertain if children played alone or if they were supervised by adults.

The ludic activity performed in the cult place of Kharayeb may be a metaphorical operator referring to the growing up process and acquiring different skills, following the suggestions of a recent article by Véronique Dasen.¹⁰⁸ The figurines' buyers may have aimed to visualize both the social images of their children and the representation of their intimate world made of uncertainty and emotion. They also wished to create a metaphorical space allowing the transfer of family and collective memory.¹⁰⁹

In this way, terracotta figurines depicting games and children activities also reveal their close connection to rites of passage, linked to the growth, and the many changing of status from the wild spontaneity of childhood to the sense of responsibility of adulthood, a necessary step in achieving maturity both for boys and girls living in that multicultural milieu of Hellenistic Phoenicia.

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108 Cf. Dasen, 2018b.

109 Cf. Bellia, 2014; Dasen, 2016.

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Fig. 1. Map with central and eastern Mediterranean sites. Elaboration by the author.

Fig. 2. Map of the sanctuary of Kharayeb. After Oggiano, 2018, p. 22, fig. 7.

Fig. 3. Chart with the types and percentages of the Hellenistic figurines from Kharayeb. Elaboration by the author.

Fig. 4. Chart with the types and percentages of the Hellenistic children from Kharayeb. Elaboration by the author.

Fig. 5. Child with a goose, from Kharayeb. After Chéhab, 1953-1954, pl. LVIII, 5.

Fig. 6. Child feeding and/or teasing a bird with a bunch of grapes, from Kharayeb. Composition by the author after Chéhab, 1953-1954, pl. XLIX, 4 and photographs by Ida Oggiano.

Fig. 7. Child protecting a bunch of grapes from a duck, from Kharayeb. After Chéhab, 1953-1954, pl. LIII.

Fig. 8. Child training a Maltese dog with a ball, from Kharayeb. Composition by the author after Chéhab, 1953-1954, pl. LIX, 2, and photographs by Ida Oggiano.

Fig. 9. Boy standing with a ball, from Kharayeb. Composition by the author after Chéhab, 1953-1954, pl. LIX, 3 and photographs by Ida Oggiano.

Fig. 10. Male and female pupils, from Kharayeb. Composition by the author after Oggiano, 2015b, p. 264, fig. 9d and Chéhab, 1953-1954, pls. LXIII, 4, LXIV, 1, LXV, 2-4.

Fig. 11. Female figurine holding the *platagé*, from Kharayeb. Composition by the author after Chéhab, 1953-1954, pl. XLII, and photographs by Ida Oggiano.